

Recognized Pattern from S-Spectrum of 1-D and 2-D Gravity Data *Applicable for depiction of the Earth's Interior Density Inhomogeneities*

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Abstract: The physical parameters of underground sources are projected to the spectrum of data in wavenumber domain. Some transformation, like Wavelets and S-transforms, can locally depict wavelength events due to source parameter variations in the position-wavenumber space. When the anomaly is depicted in wavenumber-position plane, in fact, its boundaries are detected; it seems that the transform can make a simulating model of underground source. Hence, the perspective imaginations of the buried structures, in 2-D or 3-D, are obtained and the transformation can be considered as a pattern for depicting anomalies. Although, there are always limiting conditions which are suggested to proper usage of an instrument. In this paper, an anomaly visualization technique by using S-transform of gravity data is proposed in which the spectrum approximates the size and the shape of anomalies. Based on expected facts, the capabilities of S-spectrum were tested through synthetic examples; in addition, new techniques were found for optimal condition of application of S-transform for anomaly depiction. It was illustrated that in order to depict the anomalies clearly, the 2-D S-transform of gravity data is more effective than 1-D one. Regarding the density inhomogeneity of mantle plume in Iceland, the 2-D S-transform was effective in visualization of the probable hotspot area. This area was invisible compared with other denser areas and was not being modelled through other methods, quantitatively.

1 INTRODUCTION

In every geologic province the physical parameters are unique and the prospective gravity anomaly signature associated with each individual area will vary accordingly (Prieto, 1996). Preliminary estimation of buried structures could be made by original gravity maps, but some analysis could be better possible throughout the application of the transformed data. S-transforms provide localized spectrum of signal (e.g., gravity data) in which the events with various wavelengths are detected in wavenumber domain. The wavelengths of events in the gravity signal vary due to physical properties of sources (anomalies) including their size or density. The study of various gravity data map and their spectrums can be helpful in finding a pattern for data analysis. This pattern is useful for previous steps to interpretation (e.g. the choosing of area for investigation purpose or quality analysis) and the matter of choosing 1-D or 2-D analysis.

There are various transformations for spectral analysis of gravity data. The Fourier transforms

(Odegard and Berg, 1965); (Mareshal, 1985); (Gupta, 1988) and power spectrums (Garcia-Abdeslem, 1995) have been widely used in analysing gravity data. The Fourier transforms provide an excellent wavenumber resolution but loses position-localization ability. The local changes of a spectrum with position are more useful than the spectrum of the whole gravity data. The need for methods of position-wavenumber localization led to the development of the Gabor transform, the Wavelet transform (Goupillard et al., 1984); (Rioul and Vetterli, 1991), the Short Time Fourier transform (Gabor, 1946), and the S-transform (Stockwell et al., 1996); (Mansinha et al., 1997). In the Wavelet transform, a sliding window function with the fixed width was introduced in Fourier integral, which has a property of the position localization at the expense of wavenumber resolution (Zhong et al., 2013).

The Fourier spectrum of a basis wavelet depends on the Mother Wavelet and the scale factor. A combination of cosinusoids, determined by its specific spectrum, provides each wavelet. Therefore,

unless one develops a feel for the spectral content of the basis wavelets, the intuitive understanding of high and low sinusoidal wavenumbers is lost (Mansinha et al., 1997). Although, both the Wavelet transform and the Short Time Fourier transform are adaptive to deal with the non-stationary signal, the Short Time Fourier transform with fixed window width cannot simultaneously obtain good spatial and wavenumber resolution. Wavelet transform profilometry uses the scale factor instead of wavenumber concept to analyse the gravity data (Zhong et al., 2013)

The S-transform provides with better position-wavenumber characteristics, by using a Gaussian window whose width and height scale inversely and linearly with the wavenumber respectively. The basis for the S-transform is Gaussian modulated sinusoids, so that it is possible to use intuitive notions of sinusoidal wavenumbers in interpreting and exploiting the resulting position-wavenumber spectrum (Mansinha et al., 1997). The merits of the Windowed Fourier (short time Fourier) analysis and Wavelet Transform are combined in S-transform beside some more advantages.

There is a direct relation between the S-transform and the natural Fourier transform which cannot be achieved by wavelets (Senapati and Routray, 2011); so, this method can be directly reversed back to position domain. Because of the application of the variable Gaussian window, it is capable of providing higher temporal resolution in low wavenumbers and higher spectral resolutions in high wavenumbers comparing with the windowed Fourier transform (Zhong et al., 2013). Gravity maps act as image in position domain and the 1-D S-transform analyses carry out row by row. Performing transform in one direction makes the application of the wavenumber information in another direction to be ignored which loses the measurement accuracy. The 2-D S-transform can be regarded as the extension of 1-D S-transform but possesses better localized position-wavenumber analysis ability (Zhong et al., 2013).

In this paper, gravity anomalies are locally detected through spectral localization of 1-D and 2-D S-transform. At first, the theory and properties of 1-D and 2-D S-transform are elaborated. In order to find the pattern of the S-transform method for visual source description, some 1-D and 2-D synthetic examples have been applied. Despite poor spectral resolution of 1-D transform, its advantages in displaying distinct anomalies and modified spectrum of gravity anomalies have been tested. It is attempted here to present evidence for density inhomogeneity

of hotspot comparing with models for seismic velocity.

Next, the 2-D S-transform coefficients are plotted to display wavenumber bands of anomalies due to synthetic and field examples. Bouguer gravity anomaly is strongly sensitive to deep structures and can reflect the negative density root of the long-wavelength structures; nevertheless, it was unable to detect hotspots in Bouguer map directly. This is a key reason for employment of S-transform in which by using the 2-D S-spectrum, the existence of hotspot, transition zone (in lower crust) have been discussed. Concluding remarks about isostasy of Iceland will be added in appendix C. Additionally, the matter of crust in a hydrostatic equilibrium, reasonability and validation of results comparing with velocity models of mantle plumes beneath Iceland are discussed.

2 THE 1-D S-TRANSFORM

The S-transform provides wavenumber dependent resolution while maintaining a direct relationship with the Fourier Transform spectrum (Stockwell et al, 1996). The expression of the original S-transform (the standard form) given by Stockwell et al. (1996) is:

$$S(\mu, k) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(x) \left\{ \frac{|k|}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \exp\left[\frac{-k^2(\mu - x)^2}{2}\right] \exp(-j2\pi kx) \right\} dx \quad (1)$$

In Eq. 1, S denotes the S-transform of h, k is the wavenumber, and the quantity μ is a parameter which controls the position of the Gaussian window on the x-axis. The S-transform windows also satisfy the admissible condition with the advantage of fast lossless invertibility from position, to position-wavenumber, to wavenumber, and back to the position domain; hence, the usage of the S-transform is very analogous to Fourier transforms.

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{|k|}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \times \exp\left[\frac{-k^2(\mu - x)^2}{2}\right] d\mu = 1 \quad (2)$$

A simple operation of averaging the local spectra over the x-axis (positions of stations) represent transformed data in S domain as dependent on only the wavenumber. There is a direct relation between the S-transform and the natural Fourier transform which cannot be achieved by wavelets (Senapati and Routray, 2011). The basis functions for the Fourier transform $H(f)$ representation of a function of position $h(x)$ are sinusoids, functions of position of indefinite extent. The original time series $h(x)$ can

be recovered from the spectrum from Eq. 1 by use of the inverse Fourier transform (Mansinha et al., 1997):

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(\mu, k) d\mu = G(k) \quad (3)$$

Eq. 3 is indicating that the S-transform is invertible, which makes position wavenumber representation a separation tool. If the $h(x)$ is real-valued, the Hilbert transform is used to extend the real-valued function into a complex function of position. The Hilbert transform of a function $h(x)$ (Papoulis, 1997) can be interpreted as the analytic signal of a real function (Stockwell, 2007). The Hilbert transform removes the negative wavenumber in spectrum which represents the S-transform as band pass filter of the original data. The mechanics of computation of Eq. 1 and 2 involves sampling at equal intervals, which makes $h(t)$ periodic in the independent variable has the dimension of length; furthermore, wavenumbers are the analogues of frequencies (Mansinha et al., 1997), as in gravity data usage.

3 THE 2-D S-TRANSFORM

The local variations in the 2-D spectrum of Bouguer map convey visual information on anomaly boundaries and shapes. The 2-D S-transform could be applied to gravity maps to give position-localized spectrum (Mansinha et al., 1997). The 2-D S-transform is defined based on application of a 2-D Gaussian modulates of cosinusoidal functions. As in Eq. 1, the Gaussian changes shape with spatial wavenumbers k_x and k_y . The expression of the 2-D S-transform (the standard form) has been given by Mansinha et al. (1997) as follows:

$$S(x, y, k_x, k_y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(x', y') \left\{ \frac{|k_x| |k_y|}{2\pi} \times \exp\left[-\frac{k_x^2(x'-x)^2 + k_y^2(y'-y)^2}{2}\right] \exp(-j2\pi(k_x x' + k_y y')) \right\} dx' dy' \quad (4)$$

where x and y are the shift parameters controlling the centre position of Gaussian windows on the x -axis and y -axis, respectively, while k_x and k_y ($x \neq 0$; $y \neq 0$) are wavenumbers (inverse of wavelengths) related to the scale parameters in two directions (Zhong et al., 2013). The period of $h(x)$ or intervals of data determines the resolution of wavenumbers in Spectrum.

$$H(k_x, k_y) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} S(x, y, k_x, k_y) dx dy \quad (5)$$

Eq. 5 indicates invertibility property of 2-D S-transform. Like the 1-D S-transform, integration of $S(x, y, k_x, k_y)$ over the variables x, y gives the 2-D Fourier Spectrum (Mansinha et al., 1997). This is helpful for rebuild a signal from spectrum whether signal in its original form or desired signal with modified spectrum.

3.1 Interpreting the 2-D S-transform

Applying the Fourier transform definition, the 2-D S-transform of images can also be written as (Zhong et al., 2013):

$$S(u, v, f_u, f_v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left\{ H(\alpha + f_u, \beta + f_v) \times \exp\left[-\frac{2\pi^2 \alpha^2}{f_u^2} - \frac{2\pi^2 \beta^2}{f_v^2}\right] \right\} \times \exp[-j2\pi(\alpha u + \beta v)] d\alpha d\beta \quad (6)$$

Where $H(\alpha + f_u, \beta + f_v)$ is the Fourier transform of $\{h(x, y) \exp[-j2\pi(\alpha u + \beta v)]\}$. α and β are frequency variables in x and y directions, respectively. The 2-D S-transform coefficients can be obtained by the inverse Fourier transform, in which the moving 2-D spectra of $h(x, y)$ were filtered by 2-D weighted filtering windows with different widths (Zhong et al., 2013). Therefore, 2-D S-transform possesses better localized position-wavenumber analysis than 1-D S-transform.

$S(u, v, f_u, f_v)$ is a 4-D S-matrix. Since each discrete point in the image has local 2-D transforms, the 2-D S-transform is a complex function of u, v, f_u and f_v and visualization of a complex function of four variables is a problem that with measured use of colours and shading it is possible to plot a function of three variables (Mansinha et al., 1997). For any point (u, v) , its 2-D S-transform coefficients $S(f_u, f_v)$ is two dimensional S-matrixes. The range of the useful fundamental frequencies of f_u and f_v is set by calculation of the Fourier spectra. Because the height distribution of the tested object will cause the extension of the fundamental spectra of the image, f_u and f_v may be too small to lead to large size Gaussian windows, and the large windows will lead to low resolution of time in this direction, which causes a failing reconstruction (Zhong et al., 2013).

There are similar interpretations when the image is replaced with Bouguer gravity maps except frequencies are analogous to wavenumber in the

case of real gravity data. The 2-D S-transform for any point (u, v), could be plotted as a 3-D surface plot versus k_x and k_y where the z axis is the amplitude of S-transform coefficients. This is much close to Fourier concept of this transform and depicts the variable wavenumber contents of spectra in 3-D space. The same plot of 2-D S-transform coefficients could be existed which is versus x and y and again the z axis is amplitude. This kind of plot is more suitable for providing spectra due to image and maps like gravity maps. Inevitably we have to use amplitude for the z axis which represents the amplitudes due to different level coefficients. Low wavenumbers constitute the deep sources of potential fields, vice versa. Here, we have a plane instead of a profile as in 1-D S-transform; hence, the behaviour of plane upwelling and going down plane in wavenumber domain is of interest. Approximately, the summation of two wavenumbers in x and y axis could represent the wavenumber concept of plane moving downward or upward along normal direction to plane.

4 1-D AND 2-D SYNTHETIC EXAMPLES

The gravity anomaly signature characteristics are results of one or more physical parameters such as: the configuration of the anomalous zone, density contrasts, and the depth to the anomalous body (Prieto, 1996). A collection of simple structures have

b)

Figure 1. a) The first synthetic model with a single cube in the centre. b) The second synthetic model with four different size cubes, gravity sources.

been modelled, and in the followings, calculated gravity responses and their transformations are discussed to identify spectrum characteristics.

In the first example, we compute the gravity effect produced by a cube, with length of 18 km buried at a depth 15 km, with density contrast of 500 kg/m^3 (Fig. 1(a)). The gravity anomaly is calculated along the profile with a length of 100 km at intervals of 4 km.

For the second example, the gravity data is computed for four cubes that are in depth of 15 km. The density contrasts of all cubes are 500 kg/m^3 .

a)

b)

c)

Figure 2. a) Plot of gravity data relied at profile AA' which has been displayed in Fig. 1(a). b) The 1-D S-transform of gravity data of profile AA'. c) Gravity data relied at profile BB', displayed in Fig. 1(b). d) The S-transform of profile BB'. Modified S-spectrum coefficients lying on special wavenumber ranges or rows of S-matrix called as 'voice' including: e) voice 2, f) voice 4.

The well-known Talwani algorithm was used as the basis for the computations of gravity effects. The 2-D gravity effects are shown in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b). The gravity effect of profiles AA' is shown in Fig. 2-a. In addition, Fig. 2(c) shows the gravity anomaly generated from the two cubes along the profile BB'.

The 1-D S-transform of profile AA' and BB' are shown in Fig. 2(b) and 2(d). The single cube of first model provides some anomalies in wavenumber-position plane of S-transform. It is not unique spectral event because bell-like signal contains different wavenumber bands. In fact, any signal is composed of basis wavelength, inherently. In another synthetic model, multi cubes, like in second model, are employed. Although, its S-transform shows different contours, representing various wavenumbers, they are distinguishable in separated plots choosing special wavenumber bands. Localized S-spectrum detects anomalies in the horizontal direction that is useful in case of existence of some anomalies relying along the profile. But, a single cube provides wavenumber bands overlaying each other. So, the certain wavenumber bands in which anomaly locates, is ambiguously determined. Furthermore, the

Figure 3. a) The contour map of gravity data due to a) the first synthetic model, and b) the second one. 3-D plot of 2-D S-transform of data displayed in c) section a, and d) section b, respectively.

wavenumber axis can be converted to depth axis, and the spectrum act like a modelling instrument.

The 1-D S-transform of gravity data in Fig. 2(c) includes a lot of concentrated contour shapes representing anomalies. These anomalies counted as symptoms of wavenumber change in trend of data which are due to density inhomogeneity. Hence, separation of bands viz. more separated local spectrum can help us significantly in much clearly detecting the density inhomogeneity that results in the localized description of structures.

In 2-D S-transform's plot of the first model, the repetition of basis wavenumbers is seen (Fig. 3(c)). It is still existed after application of analytical signal of gravity data (which is necessary for avoiding self-aliasing effect in S-transform). Fig. 3(d) provides much localized spectrum which depicts distinguishably anomalies. However, the initial locations of anomalies have not been preserved; but, approximately, locations of anomalies in 2-D spectrum can represent the actual ones. Hence, the 2-D transformation utilizes a more effective visualization. Besides localization advantages of 2-D spectrum, the presence of some anomalies, which is

always occurred in environmental cases, provides much better separable spectrums.

5 APPLICATION TO FIELD EXAMPLE

5.1 1-D analysis of gravity anomaly of Iceland

Mantle plume, known as localized upwelling currents of solid rocks, seem hotter and thus less dense than the surrounding mantle or lower crust but still denser than the upper crust and its surroundings. There are some areas, called hotspot, in mantle plume which have density and temperature difference with whole upwelling architectures. Regarding choosing of area with geodynamical importance, Iceland is an area lying on an oceanic rift which includes an active mantle upwelling. Low velocity anomalies (ΔVS) along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge lie at different depths under the mantle plume provinces (Fig. 4(a), below part). In velocity model (Fig. 4(a)) the depth slices from shear wave velocity changes are centred at plumes (hotspots) locations

Figure 4. a) Profiles of free-air anomaly (FA) along the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (Seidler et al., 1999, their Fig. 13) b) The S-transform of gravity data.

approximately, but still do not fit well. The free-air anomalies (correspondent to the short-wavelength topography) are simultaneously plotted above. The digitized plot of free air anomalies (Fig. 4(a)) shows some maximum and minimum peaks (curvatures) due to density changes. From trend of data the minimum curvature near longitude 60 degree is probably anomaly due to Iceland.

Locations of anomalies at the data profile can with some care be picked by eye; but, are much easier to see on the S-transform. The S-transform of

Figure 5. All sections represent modified S-spectrum coefficients lying on special wavenumber bands of: a) voice 3, b) voice 4, c) voice 5, d) voice 6, e) voice 7, f) voice 8.

gravity data in Fig. 4(b) includes a lot of concentrated contour shapes. In this part, the unit of Inverse of Unit Interval (IUI) is used instead of degree reverse for wavenumber scale.

The first minimum peak was centred near St. Helena in -20 degree which was discerned visually on the relatively left anomaly in the S-transform plot (Fig. 5(e)). On the trend of data, there is an increase in wavelength at zero degree, which creates middle anomaly in Fig. 5(f). Next peak is a minimum that its position-wavenumber signatures stood out clearly on the S-transform plot as middle anomaly in Fig. 5(e). Also, it is separately figured in voice 4 at wavenumber band of 0.03 IUI (Fig. 5(b)). The maximum peak at 40 degree (Azores hotspot) was actually due to a local anomaly in wavenumber bands of 0.04, 0.05, and 0.07 IUI (voices 5, 6, and 8). However, in lower bands, its anomalies were less localized related to x-axis. Voice 8 included three anomalies correspondent for three maximum peaks which were correspondent to minimum peaks, too.

The relatively left anomaly in Fig. 5(f) was representative of maximum peak at -40 degree to the position-wavenumber plane. The lowest wavenumber included in the S-transform plot is 0.01 IUI. The first wavenumber band (Fig. 5(a)) included two anomalies at boundaries which could be related to slabs. On the S-transform visualized in Fig. 5(e),

the relatively right anomaly at 60-80 degrees depicted the Iceland. This anomaly was easier to differentiate on the S-transform than on the trend of free-air data which highlights the advantages of the proposed approach.

5.2 2-D analysis of Bouguer gravity anomaly of Iceland

Free-air anomalies are more influenced by upper crust and topography. Hence, they weakly discern mantle plume's density inhomogeneity (lying in deep layers of the Earth) due to hotspots; although, mantle structures are better recognized in Bouguer anomalies. The analysis of Bouguer anomalies leads to identification of source parameters like: depth and geometry (essential parameters of modelling) that are necessary for the initial imagination. Although, mantle anomalies of gravity data may remain masked in the space domain by a multitude of effects, tendencies may become visible in the spectra (Seidler et al., 1999).

Figure 6. Bathymetry and ridges in the North Atlantic.

Location of the Bouguer anomaly minimum (Thorbergsson et al., 1993, Shen et al., 2002) indicate a present-day location of the Iceland plume at 18° W, 64.4° N (Mihalffy et al., 2008). Additionally, bathymetry map has been plotted which shows extending from approximately -55° to 5°E and 55° to 75°N.

The map displayed in Fig. 7(a) due to isolated Iceland effects, has been plotted extending from approximately -30° to -10°w and 62° to 68°N (standard coordinates). The square grid intervals in Fig. 7(a) is 28.8 km along x-axis (labelled longitude) and 20 km along y-axis (labelled latitude). A gravity anomaly trend has extremely negative amplitude of about -40 mGal. It is important to note that this is a single anomaly which might not be detected clearly

by S-transform. But, some boundary negative effects, regarding other crustal architectures, avoids Iceland's anomaly to be left single (like in first synthetic model).

a)

b)

Figure 7. a) Bouguer gravity map of Iceland form the digitization of Bouguer anomaly map by Eysteinnsson and Gunnarsson (1995). b) 2-D S-transform of gravity data.

The local spectrum was provided related to the two position axes versus wavenumber. In Fig 7(b) the S-transform shows traces of anomalies in slices. The Bouguer map spectrum is divided into two regions in the 0.005 ~ 0.01 rad/km at low wavenumber band (long wavelength features viz. lithospheric structures) and 0.01~ 0.04 rad/km at high wavenumber part (short wavelength features viz. crustal structures). A third region is apparent in the 0.01 rad/km. The S-spectrum shows up distinguished regions that are not easily apparent in other products from the original data like gradient analysis. The lowest wavenumber band can be counted as a witness to deeply continued mantle plume.

There is a discontinuity between high wavenumber portion (crustal structures 0.01~0.04 rad/km) and low wavenumber portion (deep mantle plume 0.005~0.01 rad/km).

The gap in wavenumber bands (0.015 rad/km) of transformed gravity data of Iceland (Fig. 7(b)) seems to be related to transition zone occurred in lower crust. In the same way, thick root including complex composition of hotspots and transition zone are imaginable. Depth penetration of gravity data is lower than magnetic data; hence, the deeper structures poorly discerned by its transform. Nevertheless, the deep mantle structures and conventional cycles in analysis of Bouguer gravity data should not be entered. Besides modelling results, the isostasy condition of this dynamic area, could be explained by abundant results from localized and highly resolvable S-spectrum.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a pattern of S-transform's application for gravity anomaly depiction in position-wavenumber plane. Besides efficiency of S-transform in anomaly visualization, direct representation of spectrum related to wavenumber is very advantageous in the depth estimation methods (which is not achieved by other transformation like Wavelets). In addition, since there is a direct relationship between wavenumber and depth, the plotted spectrum could be represented as a simulated model of source in depth cross-section (x , y , and z axes of plot constitute spatial coordinates).

One of the keys for recognizing the pattern is the modelling of the synthetic structures. The comparison of various spectrums provided by the S-transform of different synthetics, illustrated a useful pattern of density inhomogeneity visualization for gravity anomalies. The 1-D S-transform of the gravity anomaly provides the localized spectrum with enough resolution. Although, using a long profile passing over some sources of potential fields provides a more resolvable trace of gravity data, relatively. The pattern of depiction was obtained from 1-D gravity data, and anomalies in spectrum were localized in wavenumber domains. They were visualized separately if the wavenumber bands would be distinguished band by band.

One of the most significant findings was the observed traces due to mantle plume. S-spectrum from 2-D S-transform provides the same description like previous velocity models for Iceland mantle

architecture; the spectrum was more localized than 1-D one, preferably. In case of field examples, existence of other lateral gravity sources helped the much localization. All findings in this paper have been counted based on limited synthetic examples and significant field examples. Even though, future works are necessary to be done to establish whether S-transform can always generate the useful results.

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REFERENCES

- Allen, R. M., 2001, The mantle plume beneath Iceland and its interaction with the North-Atlantic Ridge: A seismological investigation, Ph.D. Thesis, Princeton University.
- Brandsdottir, B., Menke, W., Einarsson, P., White, R.S., and Staples, R.K., 1997, Froe-Iceland Ridge experiment 2. Crustal structure of the Krafla central volcano: *J. Geophys. Res.*, 102, 7867-7887.
- Eysteinnsson, H., and Gunnarsson, K., 1995, Maps of gravity, bathymetry and magnetics for Iceland and surroundings: OS-95055/JHD-07 report National Energy Authority, geothermal division, 39 pages.
- Gabor, D., 1946, Theory of communication: *J. Inst. Elect. Eng.*, 93, 429-457.
- Garcia-Abdeslem, J., 1995, Inversion of the power spectrum from gravity anomalies of prismatic bodies: *Geophysics*, 60, 6, 1698-1703.
- Gudmundsson, Ó., 2003, The dense root of the Iceland crust: *Earth and Planetary Science Letters* 206, 427-440.
- Gupta, O. P., 1988, a Fourier transform minimization technique for interpreting magnetic anomalies of some two-dimensional bodies: *Canadian journal of exploration geophysics*, 24, 2, 179.184.
- Kaban, M. K., Flóvenz, ó. G., and pa'lmason, G. , 2002, Nature of the crust-mantle transition zone and the thermal state of the upper mantle beneath Iceland from gravity modeling: *Geophys. J. Int.*, 149, 281-299.
- Mansinha, L., Stockwell, R., G., Lowe, R., P., Eramian, M., and Schincariol, R., A., 1997, Local S-spectrum analysis of 1-D and 2-D data: *Physics of the Earth and Planetary Interiors*, 103, 329-336.
- Mareshal, J. C., 1985, Inversion of potential field data in Fourier transform domain, *Geophysics*, 50, No. 4, 685-691.
- Menke, W., 1999, Crustal isostasy indicates anomalous densities beneath Iceland: *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 26, 1215-1218.

Menke, W., and Levin, V., 1994, Cold crust in a hot spot: *Geophys. Res. Lett.*, 21, 1967–1970.

Mihalffy, P., Steinberger, B., and Schmeling, H., 2008, The effect of the large-scale mantle flow field on the Iceland hotspot track: *Tectonophysics*, 447, 5–18.

Odegard, O., and Berg, J. W., 1965, gravity interpretation using the Fourier integral: *Geophysics*, xxx, 3, 424-438.

Papoulis, A., 1997, *Signal analysis*: McGraw-Hill Book Company.

Pinnegar, C. R., and Mansinha, L., 2003, The S-transform with windows of arbitrary and varying shape: *Geophysics*, 68, No. 1, 381–385.

Prieto, C., 1996, gravity/magnetic signatures of various geologic models- an exercise in pattern recognition: *IGS footnotes series*, 4, 4, 1-26.

Rioul, O., and Vetterli, M., 1991, Wavelets and signal processing: *IEEE SP Magazine*, 8, 14-38, 1991.

Senapati, K., and Routray, A., 2011, Comparison of ICA and WT with S-transform based method for removal of ocular artifact from EEG signals: *Journal of Biomedical Science and Engineering*, 4, 341-351

Seidler, E., Jacoby, W. R., and Cavsak, H., 1999, Hotspot distribution, gravity, mantle tomography; evidence for plumes: *Geodynamics*, 27, 474-597.

Shen, Y., Solomon, S. C., Bjarnason, I. T., Nolet, G., Morgan, W. J., Allen, R. M., Vogfjrd, K., Jakubsdottir, S., Stefansson, R., Julian, B. R., and Foulger, G. R., 2002, Seismic evidence for a tilted mantle plume and north–south mantle flow beneath Iceland: *Earth Planet. Sci. Lett.* 197, 261–272.

Smallwood, J. R., 1999, Crust generated above the Iceland mantle plume: from continental rift to oceanic spreading center: *J. Geophys. Res.*, 104, 22885–22902.

Staples, R. K., White, R. S., Bransdottir, B., Menke, W., Maguire, P. K. H., and McBride, J. H., 1997, Faeroe–Iceland Ridge Experiment I. Crustal structure of northeastern Iceland: *J. Geophys. Res.* 102, 7849–7866.

Stockwell, R.G., Mansinha, L. and Lowe, R. P., 1996, Localization of the complex spectrum: The S-transform: *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 44, 998-1001.

Stockwell, R. G., 2007, Why use the S-transform? Pseudo-differential operators partial differential equations and time-frequency analysis: *Fields Institute Communications*, 52, 279–309.

Thorbergsson, G., Magnússon, I. T., and Pálmason, G., 1993, Gravity Data and Gravity Map of Iceland: *Orkustofnun Íslands, OS-93027/JHD-07*.

White, R. S., 1997, Rift-plume interaction in the North: *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. A*, 355, 319-339.

Wolfe, C.J., Bjarnason, I. Th., Van Decar, J., and Solomon, S. C., 1997, Seismic structure of the Iceland mantle plume: *Nature*, 385, 245-247.

Zhong, M., Chen, W., Wang, T., and Su, X., 2013, Application of two-dimensional S-Transform infringe pattern analysis: *Optics and Lasers in Engineering*, 51, 1138–1142.

APPENDIXES

Appendix A: Matlab script for the 1-D S-transform

The following Matlab script was used to calculate the standard 1-D S-transform when the 18-point gravity data in profile direction are entered as a vector “h”:

```
M = 18;
T = 5; % degree unit
H = [fft(h) fft(h)];
x =fliplr([1:floor(M/2) -floor(M/2)+1:0]);
W = [1 zeros(1,M-1)];
for wa=0:floor(M/2)-1;
w = abs(f+1)/sqrt(2.*pi)*...
exp( (f+1)^2*t.^2/(2*M^2));
W = fft(w/sum(w));
ST(f+1,:) = ifft(H(f+1:f+M) .* W);
End
```

x is position and wa is wavenumber, w is the Gaussian window and W its discrete Fourier transform; ST is the S-transform have the same meaning as in Eq. 1; the sampling intervals in both directions are considered as the actual sampling rate of data automatically. This script has been simplified form of Hyperbolic S-transform code provided by Pinnegar and Mansinha (2003).

Appendix B: Matlab script for the 2-D S-transform

The following Matlab script was used to calculate the 2-D S-transform shown, when the 25-point gravity data in each direction are entered as a 25*25 matrix “h”:

```
Mx= 25;
My= 25;
g200=h-(i*hilbert(h));
H(:,,1)= fft2(g200);
for i=1:25;
x(i,:)=fliplr([1:floor(Mx/2) -floor(Mx/2)+1:0]);
end
for j=1:25;
y(:,j)=fliplr([1:floor(My/2) -floor(My/2)+1:0]);
end
a=(x+y)/2;
W = [zeros(My,Mx)];
```

```

for wa=0:floor(Mx)-1;
w =abs(wa+1)/sqrt(2.*pi)*...
exp(-(wa+1)^2*a.^2/(2*Mx^2));
W = fft2(w/mean(sum(w)));
for i=1:25;
H1(i+wa,:)=H(i,,:);
H1(1:wa,:)=[];
end
for j=1:25;
H2(:,j+wa)=H(:,j,:);
H2(:,1:wa)=[];
end
Hwa=(H1+H2)/2;
s(:,,wa+1)= ifft2 ( Hwa .* W );
end

```

x is position and wa is wavenumber, w is the Gaussian window and W its discrete Fourier transform; S is the S-transform have the same meaning as in Eq. 4; the sampling intervals in both directions are considered as the actual sampling rate of data automatically.

Appendix C: Discussions on interpretation of Iceland mantle plume and hotspots

Hotspots are anomalous areas that can be associated with pressure-release melting in the hot ascending mantle plume rock. They are simulated as less dense semi-spherical shapes of hot mantle rocks. The analysis of gravity data can make a clue to lithospheric structures including crustal bodies and lithospheric mantle. There is no strong correspondence between the free-air anomalies and mantle structures, because free-air anomalies are affected largely by short wavelengths. Hotspots, known as upwelling lithospheric anomalies, have the tendency to be discerned in Bouguer gravity anomalies. The study of Bouguer anomaly in Iceland shows a negative Bouguer anomaly which imposes high thickness of a dense root beneath Iceland. The probable hotspot located below the lower crust, could be a low density zone comparing with adjacent high-density asthenosphere, and can act the quasi-root for isostatic representation of negative Bouguer anomaly over Iceland.

There are a large amount of arguments and hypothesis about crustal thickness, lower crust, and mantle plume of Iceland. Gudmundsson (2003) believes that the bulk of the change in density contrast from Iceland to adjacent ridges must occur

in the crust, not the mantle while the density of lower crust in Iceland is denser than its counterpart beneath adjacent ridges. Therefore, he did not interpret the chemical transition between mafic an ultramafic rocks to explain high density of the lower crust. Nevertheless, there are ambiguities in existence of hotspot, transition zone and mantle plume beneath Iceland. But, the existence of a plume conduit is generally in agreement with the low-velocity anomaly imaged by Allen (2001) and Wolfe et al. (1997). Furthermore, White (1997) represents that the pronounced thickened crust of the Greenland–Iceland–Faroe ridge is suspected to be a geologic record of the interaction of the mid-Atlantic ridge with the Iceland plume. Kaban and co-workers (2002) inferred that the lower crust, in Iceland must be very dense in order to satisfy the gravity in and around Iceland compiled by Eysteinnsson and Gunnarsson (1995); however, in those density anomalies, there is no signature associated with a plume (Gudmundsson, 2003).

On the other hand, the Iceland crust has been extensively studied by seismic methods (Menke and Levin, 1994); (Staples et al., 1997); (Brandsdottir et al., 1997); (Smallwood, 1999); (Mihalffy et al., 2008). Through an isostatic argument, it was demonstrated by Menke (1999) that the density contrast between the crust and mantle (between mafic and ultra-mafic composition) beneath Iceland is very low ($90 \pm 10 \text{ kg/m}^3$). Solution to isostasy problem has not exactly responded the abundant question for small scale mantle anomalies of the gravity fields, such as hotspots.

Small scale upper mantle anomalies, generally escape to be detected by tomographic methods while could be a symptom of the transition between crust and mantle. Dense upper mantle does allow upwelling the hot rocks; however, it is flowing in transition zone near lower crust at present. But, at the time being, hydrostatic equilibrium in (perhaps) transition zone or lower crust refuses upwelling to ridge. It is worthwhile to note that hypothesis for isostatic equilibrium is paradoxically affected by dynamic inherent of mantle plume and hotspot beneath Iceland.